

PRESINMED

“Preserving the singularity of Mediterranean high-mountain biodiversity hotspots: a NbS approach”

Field sampling Methods

A guidance document on field sampling protocols for Tasks 1.1, 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4

To cite this manual

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1. Sampling site selection

Sampling sites will be selected following these criteria: **aspect**, **altitude**, **moisture conditions** (wet/dry), **human pressure** or **tourism** (low/medium/high), **ungulate pressure** or **herbivory** (low/medium/high). **Table 1** presents a selection of sites chosen by the University of Granada (UGR) team in Sierra Nevada.

Figure 1 shows the conceptual design of the field sampling conducted in wet meadows (control), as well as in wet meadows that have emerged associated with a traditional irrigation channel (*acequia*), or those that have been disappearing as an *acequia* dried up. Please consider the distance between meadows to avoid overlapping sampling.

Figure 1. Conceptual design of the field sampling.

Other sampling sites will be located where partners plan to do active restoration activities. Water supply can be achieved through the restoration of an *acequia* or artificially via irrigation, as is done in Gran Paradiso.

Ideally, sampling should also be extended to include wet meadows that have experienced changes in their occupation area due to water gain or loss

from a known date. These sites will be considered for the Remote Sensing analyses to be conducted within the project by UGR.

Table 1. Sampling sites selected by the University of Granada team for Sierra Nevada. The sites where Nature-based Solutions (NbS) will be applied are pending selection.

Meadow		Valley		Criteria			
#	Name	Name	Aspect	1 Altitude	2 Moisture	3 Tourism	4 Ungulate
1	Borreguil de San Juan 1 - wet	San Juan	N	2500	Wet	High	High
2	Borreguil de San Juan 1 - dry	San Juan	N	2500	Dry	High	High
3	Borreguil de San Juan 2 - wet	San Juan	N	2800	Wet	Low	Low
4	Borreguil de San Juan 2 - dry	San Juan	N	2800	Dry	Low	Low
5	Borreguil (NbS) - San Juan	San Juan	N				
6	Lagunillo misterioso - wet	Dílar	W	2700	Wet	Low-Medium	Low-Medium
7	Lagunillo misterioso - dry	Dílar	W	2700	Dry	Low-Medium	Low-Medium
8	Lagunillos de la Virgen - wet	Dílar	W	2900	Wet	High	High
9	Lagunillos de la Virgen - dry	Dílar	W	2900	Dry	High	High
10	Borreguil (NbS) - Dílar	Dílar	W				
11	Aguas verdes/ Río Seco - wet	Poqueira	S	3000	Wet	Low	Low
12	Aguas verdes/ Río Seco - dry	Poqueira	S	3000	Dry	Low	Low
13	Borreguil (NbS) - Poqueira	Poqueira	S				

2. Variables and measurement methods

Table 2 summarizes the variables to be measured for each task, along with the proposed method. Field sampling will be conducted twice a year: in late July and early September (for 2-3 years), while orthophoto analysis will be performed once (using the last available orthophoto).

Table 2. List of variables to be measured for each task and the proposed method. The 'ha' units refer to the total area (in hectares) occupied by the meadow and its area of influence (a 50-meter perimeter buffer).

Task		Variable	Unit	Method
1.1	Herbivory	Disturbed soil cover	%	Field sampling
		Nitrophilous/colonizers plant cover	%	
		Ungulate droppings cover	%	
1.2	Tourism	Litter (rubbish) cover	%	Orthophoto
		Visitors density	n° visitors/ha	
		Path density	m of path/ha	
		Overnight pens density	n° pens/ha	
		Parking proximity distance	m	
		Meadow area	ha	
1.3	Biodiversity	Birds count	n° individuals	Field sampling
		Plant cover	cover by species (%)	
		Invertebrate fauna count	n° individuals	
1.4	CO2 fluxes	Net ecosystem exchange (NEE)	g CO ₂ /m ⁻² h ⁻¹	Field sampling
		Ecosystem respiration (Reco)	g CO ₂ /m ⁻² h ⁻¹	
		Soil temperature	°C	
		Soil water content	%vol.	

2.1. Variables obtained from orthophotography

In the meadow and its influence area (a 50-meter perimeter buffer), the following variables will be estimated using GIS software:

- **Path density (m of path / total area):** human paths will be drawn and quantified within the total area (inside the meadow and within the influence area).
- **Overnight pens density (n° of overnight pens / total area):** pens (dry stone corrals for sleep protection used by humans to overnight) will be drawn and quantified within the total area (inside the meadow and within the influence area).
- **Parking proximity distance (m):** distance measured as optimal walking route.
- **Meadow area (ha)**

On in-situ field sampling days, the **number of visitors** within the meadow and its influence zone (50m buffer around the meadow) will be recorded. For a more reliable record of visitor numbers, it is recommended to obtain data from the Park Rangers or through automatic visitor counters installed in the area.

Figure 2. Map illustrating a sampling site and its influence area (50m buffer area).

2.2. Variables measured by field sampling (circles)

Variables are sampled inside a maximum of 20 circular plots (1m radius), or a number proportional to the meadow's area if it is small. Circles will be randomly selected at each sampling event. The variables measured in each circular plot will be:

- **Disturbed soil cover (%)**: percentage of disturbed (removed, trampled or eroded) soil covering each circular plot.
- **Nitrophilous/colonizers plant cover (%)**: a selection of species described as colonizers and/or indicators of disturbed soils will be sampled.
- **Ungulate droppings cover (%)**: percentage of cattle, sheep/goat, and horse excrements covering each circular plot. Ideally, a percentage should be provided for each category (cattle, sheep/goat, horse).
- **Coverage of litter (%)**: percentage of rubbish and type (e.g. plastic bottle, cigarette butt, etc.) covering each circular plot.

Figure 3. Map illustrating a sampling site and the methodology detailed in this section.

2.3. Variables measured by field sampling (perimeter transect)

Bird density and richness are estimated by a perimeter transect around the meadow, which will be repeated in each sampling event. All birds will be recorded on both sides of the transect, with a maximum bandwidth of 25m on each side of the transect. Please consider the distance between meadows to avoid overlapping sampling. The information collected will be:

- **Bird count:** number of individuals by species.
- **Taxon name:** scientific name of the individual(s) observed, identified to the most detailed taxonomic category possible. Please refer to the last paragraph of the document for instructions on how to provide the taxonomic lists.

Figure 4. Map illustrating a sampling site and the methodology detailed in this section.

2.4. Variables measured by field sampling (transects and quadrats)

Plant-related variables will be measured using 50cm² “intercept point quadrats” (Figure 5) distributed along transects. These transects will have a bandwidth of 1m (50cm on each side of the transect) and a variable length between 6 and 50m, depending on the size of the meadow. The number of transects also varies, ranging from 1 to 5, based on meadow size. Transects will be always distributed from the center of the meadow outwards, with the same transects repeated in each sampling event. If it's a large meadow requiring more than one transect, they will be distributed from the center outwards in the four main compass directions (North, South, East, and West). If only one or two transects are used, they will be oriented from the center towards the area where the meadow occupies the largest extent.

Figure 5. Example of an “intercept point quadrat”.

Quadrats will be placed as shown in Figure 6, in the first 50cm of each meter of the transect: the first two (left and right) are located within the initial 0-50cm of the transect line (starting from the center), the next two at 100-150cm along the transect, and so on. When recording data, quadrats will be numbered 1 to X from the center of the meadow outwards, indicating which side of the transect they are on: 1-left, 1-right, 2-left, 2-right, and so on.

Figure 6. Map illustrating a sampling site and the methodology detailed in this section.

The information collected in the quadrats will be:

- **Plant cover:** relative frequency (%), meaning the number of grids where a species appears. For example, if a species is present in 5 out of 100 quadrats, its relative frequency would be 5%. Please use a complete list of indicator species (e.g. endemic, colonizers, threatened etc.). *Optional: where vascular plants are absent in the grid, then record the element (solid rock, scree, bare ground, litter, etc.) and the number of grids completely. This can be used to calculate total vegetation cover as 100 minus the sum of empty grids.
- **Taxon name:** scientific name of the specie(s) observed, identified to the most detailed taxonomic category possible. Please refer to the last paragraph of the document for instructions on how to provide the taxonomic lists.

Insect-related variables will be measured along these same transects, but by considering individuals observed or found under stones (A4-A5) within 1 meter to the left and 1 meter to the right of the transect line. Ideally, sampling will be conducted during the warmest hours of the day. The information collected will be:

- **Arthropod count:** number of individuals of species that are of particular interest due to their uniqueness or threat level (e.g. endemic, new colonizers, threatened). All other taxa are also counted, but only identified to the Order level.
- **Taxon name:** scientific name of the individual(s) observed. Please refer to the last paragraph of the document for instructions on how to provide the taxonomic lists.

2.5. Variables measured by field sampling (next to quadrats)

Variables related to CO₂ fluxes will be measured next to the quadrats previously described. Specifically, nine PVC collars will be inserted at the rear edge of the odd-numbered quadrats on the right side of the transect, and at the rear edge of the even-numbered quadrats on the left side (Figure 7). At least two transects per meadow must be measured.

CO₂ fluxes will be measured around midday with a portable infrared gas analyzer system (IRGA) connected to a transparent chamber. The UGR team uses the model EGM-4/CPY-4 (PP-Systems, Hitchin, UK). Each collar will be measured twice. For the second measurement, the transparent chamber will be covered with an opaque blanket to exclude light and thus prevent photosynthesis. The first measurement yields the net ecosystem exchange (NEE), while the second provides an estimate of ecosystem respiration (ER). Gross primary production (GPP) will then be calculated as the sum of NEE and ER. Soil water content (SWC) and soil temperature (Ts) will also be measured next to each collar using a portable sensor. The UGR team uses the sensor SM150T from Delta-T, UK.

Figure 7. Map illustrating a sampling site and the methodology detailed in this section. Note that the sampling points (collars marked as white points) are placed on the side of the quadrats.

3. Sampling design recommendations for Statistical Analysis

A robust experimental setup is paramount to ensure the validity and reliability of findings. Three fundamental principles (randomization, replication, and blocking) are crucial for minimizing bias, increasing statistical power, and drawing accurate conclusions about ecological phenomena.

3.1. Randomization

Randomization involves the haphazard assignment of treatments to experimental units (e.g., plots, individuals, or quadrats). The primary goal of randomization is to break any systematic association between potential confounding variables and the experimental treatments. By randomizing, you help ensure that unmeasured, uncontrollable factors are distributed evenly across your treatment groups, rather than accumulating in one particular group and falsely appearing to be an effect of your treatment. Without randomization, any observed differences could be attributed to these pre-existing variations rather than the fertilizer itself. In this project, taking into consideration practicalities (that often prevent from developing solid experimental designs), randomization may be applied by randomly selecting the plan of each sampling day (changing the order in which sites are visited), so that changes in temperature or similar along the day affect evenly to the results. Furthermore, when possible and practical, technicians may be randomly assigned sampling duties, so that technical performance is not confounded with relevant experimental factors under study.

3.2. Replication

Replication allows us to estimate the inherent variability within your experimental system. Without it, we cannot determine if an observed difference between treatments is a genuine effect or simply due to random chance. Secondly, replication increases the precision of your estimates of treatment effects. The more replicates we have, the more confident we can

be that your sample mean accurately reflects the true population mean. Finally, sufficient replication is necessary for valid statistical inference. Statistical tests rely on the variability among replicates to determine the significance of treatment effects. As a general guideline, aiming for at least 3-5 replicates per treatment is often recommended, though the optimal number depends on the expected variability of the response variable and the desired statistical power.

A warning about pseudo-replicates. Replicates which are not independent due to time or space relationships are considered pseudo-replicates and should be averaged, since their direct use in statistical inference artificially inflates the number of degrees of freedom and generates statistical tests that are too optimistic (inflated type I error). Therefore, when possible, experimental designs should consider true replicates. Pseudo-replicates are only useful to improve the reliability of measurements (by taking averages) but should never be considered a substitute for real replicates.

3.3. Blocking

Blocking is a technique used to account for known or suspected sources of variation that are not of primary interest but could influence the experimental outcome. A "block" is a group of experimental units that are more homogeneous than the entire set of units. Within each block, all treatments are applied. For instance, if you are studying the effect of different grassland biodiversity, and you know there's a significant moisture gradient across your study site, you could establish blocks along this gradient (e.g., "wet block," "medium block," "dry block"). Within each block, the experimental design is repeated. This way, you remove the variation due to the moisture gradient from the experimental error, thereby increasing the sensitivity of your experiment to detect the true effects of interest. Blocking effectively isolates unwanted sources of variation, leading to more powerful and precise statistical analyses. Think of blocking to correct for any major source of variance that you may expect (daily variation, technical variation, seasonal variation, etc.). For any inquiries regarding data analysis, please contact josecamacho@ugr.es.

4. Sampling design recommendations for Data Management

4.1. Spatial information

Partners should upload the generated spatial information to GeoNode (<https://geonode.obsneve.es/>). For any inquiries regarding this tool, please contact ricuni@ugr.es. Regarding the spatial information of the sampling sites, it is critical that the GIS IDs of the shapefile correspond to the IDs provided in the data templates (please refer to Section 4.2. for more information). The shapefile (EPSG: 4326) must contain at least the following attributes: meadow ID, meadow name, altitude, valley name, valley orientation, humidity conditions (wet/dry), human pressure (low/medium/high), livestock pressure (low/medium/high).

4.2. Field data

Field data collected by partners will be stored in a centralized database (PostgreSQL-PostGIS). To ensure data standardization, partners should submit data using the provided data templates:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1k2oecMvOfohxdco_LQ7-IB_4lnjScRGf-Y_uNflwAWM

Data should be submitted within **2 months** after the field sampling campaign to: andrearos@ugr.es. This contact can also address any data management queries you may have (e.g., Data Management Plan, data organization, etc.).

Additionally, to facilitate taxonomic information management, partners should submit the taxonomic information for all sampled organisms (plants, invertebrates and birds). The submission should include a list with the full scientific names of the taxa (with authorship), the taxon rank, as well as its associated taxonomic information (Order, Family, Genus, etc.). Please, for more details, consult template #8 from the link above.